

Appendix B: Interview Questions

RQ1: Perception and Attitudes Toward OTA

1. When you hear the term “OTA update,” how would you describe it in your own words?
2. In your opinion, how important is it for your products to have OTA capability? What makes you feel this way?
3. If OTA updates were suddenly unavailable or disabled for this product, what would be the consequence for your business? (Options: Minor inconvenience; Increased support or maintenance cost; Inability to fix security or compliance issues; Loss of access to certain markets or customers; Product would become commercially unviable)
4. From your experience, what do you think are the main advantages of having OTA updates for your company or your customers?
5. Are there any concerns or downsides that come to mind when considering OTA support?
6. What experiences or situations have most influenced how your company thinks about OTA updates?
7. What percentage of resources do you allocate to the following areas: Hardware engineering; Software feature development; OTA update and post-launch bug fixing and functional maintenance; Cloud infrastructure, backend API, and platform integration; Certification, compliance, and documentation?

RQ2: Deployed OTA Practices

1. For one of your main products, can you describe step-by-step how a firmware update goes from development to being delivered to the device?
2. Do your different product models or categories use the same update process, or are there differences? If so, what kind of differences?

3. How often do your products typically receive updates after release? Is the timing regular or more event-driven?
4. How is the update actually delivered to the device? For example, does the device check for updates automatically, through an app, or through another method?
5. When an update is being installed on a device, what do you do to make sure the update process won't fail or cause problems for users?
6. For regions like the EU which are gradually making OTA features mandatory, will the product only comply for this region or globally?
7. For products that are sold under multiple brand labels, how is OTA typically handled? Do different labels use separate OTA channels, or do they share the same backend and update pipeline?
8. Across different branded variants of the same product, are firmware images identical, or are there label-specific differences? In particular, are cryptographic mechanisms (such as signing keys, certificates, or encryption schemes) shared across labels or separated?
9. Have you encountered cases where a bug or security issue discovered in one branded variant affected other variants because they shared OTA infrastructure or firmware components?
10. In your final OTA release pipeline, where does the code signing physically happen? Do you sign the binary offline using keys that never leave your premises, or do you upload the raw binary to the cloud platform and allow their Key Management Service to apply the signature?
11. When you upload firmware to your cloud platform provider, do you maintain full control of the code signing keys, or does the cloud provider handle the signing process?
12. Have changes made by the cloud platform (for example API changes, service updates, policy updates) ever created new security risks for your

deployed devices, even though those changes were not security-related?

13. If your cloud platform provider were compromised today, would the attacker be able to push malicious firmware to your devices? Would you be able to detect it?
14. Have you ever experienced a security incident related to OTA updates or OTA infrastructure (including update delivery, control, or monitoring)? If yes, was the incident mainly related to your own systems, the cloud platform, or the interaction between the two?

RQ3: Supply Chain Responsibility Allocation

1. In your experience, when an OTA update is needed, which parties in the supply chain are usually involved in making it happen?
2. How would you describe your company's own role in the OTA process, and where do you see the responsibilities of other parties beginning and ending?
3. When updates involve multiple parties (such as chipset vendors, SDK providers, or brand customers), how does coordination typically work?
4. Have you encountered cases where it was not clear who should handle an update or a security fix? What usually happens in those situations?
5. Do business agreements or customer relationships affect who takes responsibility for maintaining OTA updates? If so, how? If not, why not?

RQ4: OTA Costs and Lifecycle Decisions

1. When you look at the total cost of supporting OTA updates for a product, can you estimate the total cost of all OTA-related expenses? How would you break that cost down into different parts?
2. For a product, can you estimate at what shipment volume OTA becomes economically "worth it" in relation to costs?
3. When your company decides to offer OTA updates for a product, what parts of the work tend to require the most resources or budget?

4. Besides the obvious development work, are there any less visible costs or efforts that come with maintaining OTA updates over time? Can you give me a breakdown of the cost categories in general?
5. Do OTA-related costs influence how long you keep a product in active maintenance or how long you continue releasing updates? If so, how?
6. For products with different price levels or target markets, do OTA costs affect how much ongoing support each product receives? What is the business model you use to determine the support length based on the various costs?
7. After a product is already sold and deployed, has anyone else in your supply chain ever made a change that increased your security or OTA maintenance cost—even though you did not change the product yourself? For example, a chip vendor, SDK provider, cloud platform, or reseller changing their rules, prices, or requirements.

RQ5: Technical and Economic Constraints

1. For some of your products, are there technical reasons that make it harder to support reliable OTA updates? If so, what are the main challenges?
2. Do the chipsets, SDKs, or software platforms you use place any limits on how OTA can be implemented? Do you need to pay upstream or downstream players? Can you explain in detail?
3. What kinds of issues have you seen when deploying OTA updates in real devices, especially when devices are widely distributed or used in different environments?
4. From a business perspective, are there situations where the cost or required resources make it difficult to offer OTA support on certain products?
5. Are there security controls or update strategies that you would like to implement at the device level but cannot express through the platform's OTA interface?
6. As a team constantly moving to new products, how difficult is it to maintain the build environment for a product you shipped 3 years ago? Have you ever found that you physically couldn't

release a security patch for an older device because the development tools or libraries were obsolete or lost?

7. Have you successfully been able to charge customers for ongoing OTA security support? If not, is the barrier technical, or do you find that consumers simply refuse to pay for “maintenance”?
8. The CRA essentially mandates security updates for the “expected product lifetime” (often 5+ years). For a low-margin product without a subscription fee, does your current pricing model actually cover 5 years of engineering and cloud costs? If not, will this regulation force you to abandon the low-end market entirely?